

Work Plans: A tool for suggesting implementation strategies to improve the FAIRness of data repositories

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Abstract

Improving the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability (or “FAIRness”) of digital resources has become increasingly important since the publication of the “FAIR Principles” in 2016. As an advocate of the FAIR Principles, GO FAIR US has developed a methodology for assessing the FAIRness of repositories. By involvement in a myriad of data landscaping projects across health research and geosciences, GO FAIR US’s analytical approach has been tested, improved, and demonstrated to be a valuable practice. Crucially, GO FAIR US’s approach focuses on the need to gather feedback from the repositories and stakeholders involved in said repositories. In this paper, we describe a way to organize the rich data collected and presented in clear work plans for implementing changes recommended through the FAIRness assessment process.

Keywords

Open science, FAIR Principles, FAIR Assessment, Data management

1. Introduction

While the FAIR Principles have gained a lot of traction in science data repository communities since 2016, the understanding of what the Principles mean for individual repositories and the ways in which they can be implemented varies (Jaconbsen et al., 2020). One of the key features of GO FAIR US’s work is to help assess the degree to which repositories and repository ecosystems adhere to the FAIR Principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability (Wilkinson et al., 2016). We call this a repository’s or ecosystem’s “FAIRness.” For

simplicity, we will refer to the assessment of unique repositories, which are “target repositories.” The assessment process is delivered by the “FAIR assessment team,” which is made up of (i) independent experts from GO FAIR US, and (ii) a range of relevant stakeholders of the target repository, such as managers, administrators and users. This diversity of input ensures a keen understanding of how the target repository operates in practice (Hoebelheinrich et al., 2025). GO FAIR US’ assessment process hinges on a “persona” framework that enables an inclusive process for target repository stakeholders, which often elucidates gaps between a target repository’s stated goals, their actual services, tools and underlying system structures and operations, and science data repository community practices developed to meet the requirements of the FAIR Principles. The persona-specific methodology and the present paper is closely tied with GO FAIR US’s work improving the FAIRness of data ecosystems at the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID, 2024). The result of this gap analysis is an actionable report called a Work Plan.

Work Plans are key deliverables of a FAIRness assessment. Work Plans are unique to their target repositories, describing how they can improve their FAIRness. A repository’s Work Plan effectively represents (i) GO FAIR US’s understanding of a repository’s approach to FAIR implementation based on data gathered during the assessment process, and (ii) a set of strategies for improving the repository’s FAIRness and increasing scientific impact. The main focus and intention of the Work Plan is to initiate discussions with a repository’s stakeholders, including its funders, to achieve the following objectives:

1. Identify opportunities to enhance FAIR adoption within the context of the repository’s own goals and objectives;
2. Explain the link between its architectural and implementation choices, its FAIRness, and the experiences of its users;
3. Improve their researchers’ ability to produce impactful science; and ultimately
4. Enable a more interoperable and impactful data ecosystem.

Work Plans evolve through at least two discernible stages: a Preliminary Work Plan, and a Final Work Plan. Preliminary Work Plans contain the initial recommendations of a FAIR assessment team for a range of tasks organized within a strategic area, with expected outcomes that will enable the repository’s goals through the increased application of the FAIR Principles. Preliminary Work Plans may be accompanied by other documentation that summarizes the information discovered about a repository’s FAIR practices, and describes the resulting recommendations. Following discussions with the target repository, a Final Work Plan is agreed upon following an iterative process informed by what the target repository deems achievable given their resource constraints, mission and goals.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the motivations and process of co-creating a Work Plan with stakeholders of the target repository, as well as key findings from previous implementations. Section 3 outlines the entire Work Plan, a template for which is available in the appendix. Section 4 then introduces certain complexities we have found are worth keeping in mind when implementing a Work Plan.

2. Work Plan Methodology

2.1. Background Work

Improving the FAIRness of a data repository requires a clear but flexible approach informed by empirical data from diverse sources. This approach culminates the extensive research and analysis done by creating a Work Plan. The Work Plan builds on two major processes: profiling the target repository, and engaging with its stakeholders.

When approaching a repository to improve its FAIRness, GO FAIR US begins by conducting desk-based research to develop the target repository’s “profile.” A repository’s profile contains basic summary information (e.g., name, organization and scientific domain) and detailed FAIR-related information (e.g., the standards used for metadata schema and ontologies and data curation services). This information is gathered from publicly available domain and research data literature, the target repository’s website, and other written documentation, such as curation manuals and data dictionaries (Hoebelheinrich et al., 2025). The initial profile is further fleshed out as more information becomes available during the entire assessment process.

Figure 1. FAIR Assessment Stages.

Secondly, the FAIR assessment team gathers data through a series of questionnaires and interviews with repository stakeholders (see the questions in Appendix 1). In particular, GO FAIR US engages stakeholders according to one of four personas: repository program officers or managers, repository staff with technical or service responsibilities, repository users contributing data, and repository users downloading data. At the very least, FAIR assessment teams gather data through the questionnaire from the first two personas. Questions are divided into sections: (i) Introduction and Demographics, (ii) FAIR Support, and (iii) FAIR Practices. Questions in the FAIR Practices section ask individuals about repository standards as they relate to specific FAIR sub-principles. For example, for FAIR Principle F1—“(Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers”—we ask: “Does your repository use ORCIDs or other digital personal identifiers for researchers?” FAIR Support questions relate more broadly to guidance provided for repository users or to data curation operations, e.g., “Please describe any criteria that your data curators/stewards use to determine the appropriateness of adding data to your repository.” Questionnaire responses are then enriched through follow-up interviews.

With this, the FAIR assessment team establishes a deep understanding of the target repository’s system and data architectures, and its operational practices and processes.

2.2. An Iterative Process

The repository profile and stakeholder engagement exercises help inform a Work Plan that is built iteratively, and that is recognized as relevant by the target repository. Indeed, the Work Plan’s effectiveness relies on its accounting for the particular circumstances of a target repository, and reflecting the insights and values of the repository stakeholders who will adopt it. This is enabled by a streamlined flow of communication between the FAIR assessment team and the target repository, and a two-stage approach to building the Work Plan. (A full template Work Plan is available in *Appendix 2*.)

In the first stage, the team develops a Preliminary Work Plan. The Preliminary Work Plan contains strategies and tasks that a repository could reasonably hope to achieve over time. Although it will incorporate goals learned through the profile and stakeholder engagement exercises, the FAIR assessment team does not presume to know which strategies and tasks would be best for the repository. Rather, the wide range of FAIR-enhancing tasks offers menu items from which the repository can select its favored work.

The Preliminary Work Plan includes more options than repositories can typically implement, and so, is usually tempered with input from other stakeholders – such as funders or division managers – who know the repository’s focus, mission and goals. To provide a balanced view of the target repository’s FAIR practices and FAIR-related choices, i.e., its FAIRness, the Preliminary Work Plan can be accompanied by a document that outlines the key areas in which the target repository engages in successful and productive FAIR practices, e.g., clear, publicly available data selection criteria or the entities in the data that are assigned persistent identifiers. In addition, there is an Executive Summary that addresses the intended audience, goals of the project, reminder of the assessment process, the recommendations and next steps. Given that the content of these documents represents a snapshot in time and the input made available from the target repository, the FAIR assessment team looks for feedback especially on the relevance, accuracy and completeness of the documents’ content, prioritization of recommendations, and clarity of communication.

In the second stage, after input is received from the repository’s sponsoring stakeholders, the repository leadership (usually, principal investigators, and key technical staff) receives the Preliminary Work Plan and its accompanying documents with an invitation to meet in the near future. During the meeting with the repository leadership, presentations and discussions cover the following points:

- All of the recommendations in the Preliminary Work Plan are strategies for FAIR adoption intended to address repository goals and objectives that the FAIR assessment team observed during the assessment process;
- Any details present or missing that help the repository team to choose, prioritize and refine strategies and tasks;
- The assistance that the FAIR assessment team could provide in contributing to or guiding the implementation of some tasks, with a focus on relevant use cases, and technological solutions; and
- The desire to participate in follow-up meetings with the FAIR assessment team.

The extent and nature of follow-up requested by the target repository can vary depending upon the repository staff’s understanding about the strategies recommended, how the strategies relate to the FAIR Principles and how feasible their implementation would be. Upon completion of the follow-up discussions and any further explanations, a Final Work Plan is co-developed with the repository team’s choice of taking on specific strategies and related tasks. The agreed-upon Final Work Plan describes the work most valuable and feasible for the repository to pursue, and includes the necessary details for the repository team and FAIR assessment team to collaborate on implementing the plan should such collaboration be desired.

3. Work Plan Components

A full Work Plan Template is available for download and reuse in the appendix. This section introduces the template’s content, including its sections and work categories.

The GO FAIR US team conceived the Work Plan as a comprehensive and canonical presentation of the tasks necessary to make a repository advanced in all the aspects of FAIR. Although we anticipated that each repository’s Work Plan would be highly specific to that repository’s initial architecture and integration of FAIR elements, we quickly found the core work categories fit any repository. Many of the specific task suggestions were appropriate for most or all of the repositories. As a result, we developed the Work Plan Template to make assembling each Work Plan more straightforward, and to remind us of the elements required for a highly FAIR repository. We can then tailor each repository’s Preliminary Work Plan based on our detailed assessment.

3.1. Document Status and Work Plan Summary

The first two subsections of the Work Plan provide information about the Work Plan. The Document Status section is for version control, and the Work Plan Summary section contains contact details about both the FAIR assessment team and the target repository.

3.2. Work Categories

The “Work Categories” section introduces the five strategies” section.

The Work Categories are:

- **PID Strategies.** PID strategies promote the use of globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers (GUPRI) (Juty et al., 2020). By “globally unique,” we mean that the identifier is a name that is specific to the digital artefact at hand. By “persistent,” we mean that the identifier needn’t change due to updated infrastructures or dependencies. And by “resolvable,” we mean resolvable in a browser for humans or computers. All of these features increase the value of the identified data and metadata to the scientific researchers, as they can discover, scrutinize, reuse or reproduce pertinent results, and cite the identifiers in documentation and publication. An example PID strategy could be “Going forward, implement PIDs for people, organizations and controlled vocabulary terms that can be used for attribution or other authoritative information.”
- **Metadata Strategies.** Metadata strategies focus on improving the findability, availability and usability of the data. This makes it easier to discover the data, get access to it (depending on permissions), understand the context in which it is being used or generated, and re-use it for validation of scientific research or pursuing new scientific discoveries. The strategies also simplify the effort required for scientific communities to work together on shared problems. An example Metadata strategy could be “Share domain-centric approaches used that other domain repositories or data contributors can support or adopt, e.g., by identifying specific metadata schemes, controlled vocabularies, data formats.”
- **Community Development Strategies.** These strategies explicitly address the ability of research communities to work together, to understand and to define their own discipline’s needs and any transdisciplinary needs, and to ensure their community’s objectives are well met. Indeed, community-driven practices can play a significant role in promoting open science and better data science practices (Armeni et al., 2021). When these strategies are implemented, scientific cooperation within specific communities or domains and across domains can be enhanced while making the sharing process more efficient and effective. An example Community Development strategy could be “Modify existing Data Sharing and Data Use Agreements, or Citation Guidelines to add recommendations that will facilitate the creation of citations for key entities such as datasets or studies.”
- **Architectural Strategies.** From a FAIR implementation point of view, architectures are the means to set up structures designed to support a number of functions related to data/metadata: their secure housing and storing, search and discovery, access and retrieval, aggregation and collection, and provision of secure and efficient connections to other systems and services, such as analytical and publishing tools. Ideally, an architecture for a repository also facilitates the workflow associated with the functions above, and allows various views of the data and the transfer of data from original sources to re-users (for discussion of a workflow for health data that includes an example architectural strategy supportive of a

Figure 2. FAIRification Strategies and Methods to Enhance Science.

generic FAIRification workflow, see Sinaci et al., 2020). Incorporating strategic architectural choices can make a given repository’s data and metadata more easily ingested, stored, discovered and used, and subsequent repository products more often cited. An example Architectural strategy could be for a repository to transform dataset metadata into a format that can be harvested by other repositories or services (e.g., JSON-LD) and expose them via an OpenAPI-compatible application program interface (API).

- **“Carpe Diem” Strategies.** Each target repository has its own mission, goals and user needs. Implementing solutions to the established or new user needs might well be undertaken when opportunities arise due to additional grant funding, the acquisition of knowledgeable staff, and the redevelopment and adaptation of tools and services that can serve multiple purposes. The specific approaches identified in this section can simplify the implementation of effective data services. The approaches suggested might help the target repository provide more consistency, and/or streamline tools or services for their users. Typically, approaches are fine-tuned to the specific circumstances of a repository, but might also identify an opportunity that could be taken with other repositories in a data ecosystem. An example Carpe Diem strategy might be to ensure users’ knowledge of the persistence strategy of the target repository by means of a preservation statement available on the repository’s website or by gaining Core Trust Seal (n.d.) certification.

3.3. Table Key

The fourth section of the Work Plan Template introduces the nomenclature used throughout the “Detailed Strategies” section, and explains how to interpret and populate its seven columns. The GO FAIR US team developed the table key and underlying assumptions based on their own experiences. The table key includes the names for the column headings in the Work Plan. The column headings are: (i) Item number, (ii) Priority, (iii) FAIRification task description, (iv) Expected Outcome, (v) FAIR principle, (vi) Metrics, and (vii) Resources required, dependencies, and Notes. Definitions are given for each column heading.

The table key also describes information about how the strategic categories, the specific strategies within a strategic category, and the tasks outlined to guide the specific strategies within the Work Plan are ordered and prioritized from the point of view of the assessment team. The order and priority suggested by the assessment team may depend on the assessment team’s sense of sequencing and dependencies, although the order and priority for each may change based on target repository or division priorities.

For the purpose of comparison and planning, the table key also includes an explanation of the effort and resources needed for each task under a specific strategy. The effort indicators roughly capture how much time a certain task will require. The effort indicators should be considered open to discussion, as the assessment of effort should be tempered with the target repository’s goals, architectures, priorities, and software development capabilities. The effort indicators range from a “modest” effort (up to a working week for most tasks) to a major effort (requiring at least some months to complete).

3.4. Detailed Strategies

This section captures the strategies co-developed by the FAIR assessment team and the target repository’s stakeholders. It is organized and underpinned by the content of the previous four sections. The Work Plan Detailed Strategies section is the place where the most specific recommendations are offered to the target repository. Not all of the strategic categories may be included in a Work Plan. Within a strategic category, not all strategies may be applied, and not all tasks within a strategy may be recommended.

In the excerpt from the Generic Work Plan template in Table 1, the FAIR assessment team would analyze the value of including a PID implementation strategy and note that some improvements could be made in the target repository’s approach to presenting citation preferences for their datasets. In the analysis, they may ascertain that only Tasks C, D and E are relevant for improving the target repository because Tasks A and B are already being accomplished, but could be augmented to achieve better results related to the F1, F2 and F4 principles. The indication of effort for Tasks C, D and E are higher and thus larger in scope, but the benefits achieved would presumably be greater as well.

Table 1. Sample PID Strategy sections from the Generic Work Plan template.

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
1		Persistent Identifier (PID) Implementation Strategies These strategies focus on identifying the data and metadata artifacts, and their component entities, using identifiers that are globally unique, persistent, resolvable in a browser for humans or computers, and citable in documentation and publications. All of these features increase the value of the underlying data and metadata to the scientific researchers, and to anyone else who wants to discover or work with the resulting resources.				
[...]						
1.4	High: A, B Medium: C, D, E	PID Strategy: Dataset Citation A) Present to submitters the format and use of citation strings for datasets and data files (using corresponding identifiers) in addition to publications. B) Publish the citation strings on the site for each dataset. C) Identify data sets in the best way possible, and report results to data providers and repo managers D) Add citation information to presented information in the repository. E) Evaluate the prospects of adding dataset identifier/citation fields to ClinicalTrials.gov.	Increased familiarity with, adoption of, and respect for data citations; increased visibility into dataset reuse.	F1, F2, F4	1) # of citations of repo’s citation identifiers 2) # of other references to repo’s dataset citations 3) Altmetrics value for repo’s datasets	Effort: ⏳ Dependencies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data citation and identification strategies can work hand-in-hand. • GO FAIR US can suggest best options for citation strings for the repo. • GO FAIR US could offer tracking strategies to detect dataset citations of all of the repo’s datasets. This is a large scope item but would have benefits across many repos.

A specific strategy that can be considered to take less effort is one from the Community and Assessment Strategies category: “Assess Strategies for Expanding Domain Researcher Data Sharing and Reuse.” The example illustrated in Table 2 shows that the first three tasks associated with this strategy have higher priority than the last two, but all of them together are considered to take less effort while addressing FAIR principles F4 and I1.

Table 2. Sample Community Assessment Strategies section from the Generic Work Plan template.

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
3		Community and Assessment Strategies These strategies explicitly address the ability of research communities to work together, to understand and define their own discipline’s needs and any transdisciplinary needs, and to ensure their community’s objectives are well met. When these strategies are implemented, scientific cooperation within specific communities or domains and across domains can be enhanced while making the sharing process more efficient and effective.				
3.1	High: A, B, C Medium: D, E	Assess Strategies for Expanding Domain Researcher Data Sharing and Reuse A) Assess existing Data Sharing and Data Use Agreements to determine whether recommendations can be included that will allow the creation of citations for datasets. B) Solicit feedback from research data submitters or reusers on their experiences with the repository for purposes of assessing and improving submission and download workflows. Identify data sets in the best way possible, and report results to data providers and repo managers C) Assess whether there are other places on the repository’s public web pages where examples of recommended formats for citing published outputs from use and reuse of the datasets can be displayed prominently. D) Consider adding information about the repository to repository registries such as fairsharing, SciCrunch, etc. to expand awareness of the repository and its data. E) Assess whether more data usage metrics can be added to the download functions or to associated search methods.	Increased awareness of the repository’s existence, with improvement in both download and upload (sharing) of data sets.	F4, I1	Measure impacts on data usage statistics of expanded sharing of information about the data collections within the repository (e.g., increased number of citations, altmetrics) For a given modification or set of modifications: 1) % change in citations 2) % change in altmetrics 3) % change in visits to relevant page type 4) % change in user access requests	Effort: ⏳ Dependencies: • Notes: • These strategies more broadly evaluate project-specific opportunities for improving data sharing and re-use, with GO FAIR US team members providing significant analytical support. • Each strategy pursues targeted improvements, at relatively low cost.

3.5. Appendices to the Generic Work Plan

Appendix A lists the 15 FAIR Principles for reference.

Appendix B provides a place within the Work Plan where explanations by the FAIR assessment team can be provided that further elucidate architectural considerations important to understand the team’s recommended strategies. Alternatively, *Appendix B* can be used by target repository staff to more clearly explain their architectural choices and so, support, counter or adjust the FAIR assessment team’s recommendations, or explain why a recommendation is not feasible. For example, if a recommendation is made to add machine-readable metadata for datasets to a repository’s website, such as JSON-LD formatted metadata, the target repository could use *Appendix B* to suggest possible approaches to making that happen, assuming agreement upon the priority ranking of the recommendation.

4. Discussion

4.1. Situating a Target Repository in its Broader Data Repository Ecosystem

Quite often, a target repository does not exist in a vacuum, but is part of a larger data repository ecosystem that may share services and data via a virtual network of other repository services, various kinds of analytical tools, and/or search portals. It is in this environment that the FAIR interoperability principles are most applicable, but may be the most difficult to implement.

When applying the FAIR assessment framework that GO FAIR US has developed, we found it important to refrain from bringing a comparative—and possibly competitive—spirit to our analysis of target repositories embedded in broader data ecosystems. What we and project funders found most productive was the assessment of repositories’ FAIR maturity within ecosystems.

The concept of FAIR maturity was introduced and described in the seminal work of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group (Bahim et al., 2020). In this approach, the RDA Working Group defined data maturity indicators that were applied to data and metadata, and assigned three levels of priority: essential, important, and useful. While the concept has only recently been applied to organizational self-assessment, e.g., as a FAIR Maturity Matrix for the life sciences—see Pistoia Alliance (2025)—, FAIR maturity for organizations within data ecosystems offers language more conducive to collaborative change management, in line with GO FAIR US’s approach.

In our experience, collaborative change management has been seen by project funders as a means to meet an important goal of the FAIR assessment of repositories within data ecosystems. The goal in question is the identification of needs and opportunities for improving the FAIRness for individual target repositories within data ecosystems. Ultimately, it is not just about individual repositories but also their ability to work together to improve the overall findability and reuse of the data managed and offered by the combination of repositories, services and tools within the domain of the data ecosystem.

4.2. FAIR Maturity of Target Repository

Given that the FAIR Principles are considered to “express policy goals, not blueprints for data infrastructure building” (Wittenburg, 2018), It is not surprising that approaches to FAIR implementation vary significantly from repository to repository, even within specific data domains. Given this, the GO FAIR US assessment process begins by finding out as much as possible from target repositories about how they themselves approached FAIR implementation. Much discussion in data science literature has been generated about a variety of assessment models and metrics for measuring FAIRness. Of particular utility to GO FAIR US, the article from G. Peng et al. (2024), pulls together an excellent summary of various assessment models and methods, and proposes a FAIR-

compliance maturity matrix for improving the FAIRness of digital objects that supports our approach. Indeed, while the maturity matrix that Peng *et al.* propose focuses on FAIRness at the digital object level, the GO FAIR US **Metrics-Based FAIR Digital Object Improving Process**

Figure 3. Metrics-based FAIR digital object improvement process from Peng *et al.* (2024).

team found that an extrapolation of this matrix to the repository level is very productive. The metrics-based FAIR improvement process describes at a high level what GO FAIR US does with its repository assessments. This is illustrated in *Figure 3*.

A target repository’s FAIR maturity can also be measured with a FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP – a machine-actionable profile which describes the implementation choices made by the target repository), that compiles the FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) a repository chooses to implement the FAIR Principles (GO FAIR, n.d.). During the assessment of a repository through publicly available information, GO FAIR US attempts to develop a FIP, although a FIP is ideally created with input from the target repository team.

4.3. Tailoring Communications

In the process of gathering information from target repositories and turning that information into Preliminary and Final Work Plans, we have found it useful to tailor communications to each repository.

4.3.1. Understanding Approaches to Digital Objects

While developing a customized Work Plan for a target repository, GO FAIR US has had to take into account the different ways that repositories delineate the digital objects they collect and the impacts of those delineations on FAIR implementation choices. As an example, when looking at biomedical life science data repositories, we found a different understanding of fundamental concepts related to data versus metadata for digital objects. The variety of different digital object types—often composed of digital entities that may themselves benefit from descriptive metadata for purposes of attribution citation, provenance, or context for reuse—may not lend themselves easily to the typical considerations important for FAIRness. For example, what are the digital entities that should have metadata within an aggregation of clinical data which forms the base data of the output from an analytical tool? What metadata are needed to find that aggregation in the target repository? What metadata are needed to facilitate the reuse of that aggregation or to pull it into a different aggregation that could either affirm or extend the original study results? The answers to these questions depend on what target repository data generators and data reusers need to do their research, and are reflected in the choices made for the infrastructure and services of the target repository. From a repository assessment point of view, we found it important to weigh these differences and choices carefully when assessing the FAIR maturity of a target repository and making recommendations for the target repository to appropriately develop its FAIR maturity.

4.3.2 Opportunity or Compliance?

In assessing and discussing Preliminary Work Plans, GO FAIR US found that target repositories do not only take different approaches to FAIR implementation based on their understanding of the FAIR Principles, but they may have achieved a different level of FAIR maturity in its focus upon the FAIR Principles.

While most repositories have some notion of what the FAIR Principles are, their implementation choices may have different motivations, from compliance to opportunities. On the one hand, some repositories consider the implementation of the FAIR Principles to be an issue of compliance to an as yet unclear set of requirements that needed to be set by repository funders. On the other hand, there are repositories that consider implementation strategies to be an opportunity to extend the infrastructure and services that could be offered to their data users. The GO FAIR US team recognizes the legitimacy of each perspective, learning how best to communicate with each target repository in light of its implementation choices, and its relative FAIR maturity level. Without such careful communication, it is more difficult to make relevant and productive recommendations for changes that would further the target repository's goals with buy-in from data ecosystem leadership.

One important aspect of achieving both productive communication and collaborative work on better implementing the FAIR Principles is to refrain from being rigid FAIR “evangelists.” We needed to continually remind ourselves that there were many ways to achieve the overall goals of the FAIR principles, i.e., to make data more interoperable, and therefore, findable, accessible, and ultimately reusable. We also needed to remember that each of the target repositories was passionate about the generation and sharing of impactful science in their domain. This was reflected in their relationship with the FAIR principles and Work Plans, i.e., they were often most interested in FAIRification tasks that aligned closely with their scientific priorities as compared to implementing FAIR for its own sake.

Recognizing the differences in notions of FAIR *compliance* versus FAIR *opportunity* has proven to be pivotal in moving FAIR implementation forward for the broader data ecosystem that the GO FAIR US team analyzed. The differences in approach represent expectations of strong recommendations (or requirements) that would help repositories achieve compliance with the FAIR Principles versus the provision of opportunities to better achieve a higher level of FAIR maturity and advance a single repository's or an interdependent set of repositories' infrastructures and services.

Partway through the analysis phase of the landscaping project, the funding organization made a decision to take what GO FAIR US had discovered, recommended and heard as feedback from a representative sample of target repositories within the data landscape, and create a list of recommendations (Mayer, 2025). The recommendations were organized into a number of key areas designed to facilitate not the FAIR principles specifically, but rather better discovery, sharing and reuse of the data within their purview. Although the recommendations were easily aligned with the FAIR principles, their focus and stated impetus directly addressed the broader goal of increasing the impact of science being generated by researchers and being curated and managed by the repositories and data centers within the larger data ecosystem. This nuanced approach promises to provide a balance between the compliance and opportunities perspectives and also offers a means to adjust scoping for different kinds of funding opportunities to the repositories. More in-depth information about the specific context and content of the recommendations is out of scope for this paper. Additional papers may be forthcoming as the project continues.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we have introduced the Work Plan, a practical method for comprehensively documenting FAIRification strategies. The strategies concern repository-specific items across four major areas: persistent identifiers, metadata, community and architecture. The Work Plan is the culmination of the initial phase of a “persona-based” framework for assessing the FAIRness of repositories within data ecosystems. The persona-based framework itself helps identify key considerations and obstacles by designing a customized Work Plan. These considerations include the role of target repositories within their wider data ecosystems, their FAIR maturity, and their own understanding of digital entities and FAIRness as either questions of opportunity or compliance.

Our high-level strategy distinguishes our approach from that taken by most individual repositories that are inevitably constrained by development resources, maturity of FAIR vision and understanding, and engineering expertise. We recognize that our team has the luxury of surveying and representing the landscape of FAIR implementation practices, and that no single repository can or should try to achieve some “perfect FAIRness level.” Our Work Plan process accounts for the real-world limitations faced by repository funders, managers, and developers by supporting a decision-making process that evaluates the tradeoffs involved in each recommendation.

As part of a comprehensive landscaping exercise, either for one or a number of data resources, the Work Plan is a powerful decision-making and prioritization tool. While the task of increasing any repository’s FAIRness is always limited by resource constraints, the Work Plan provides a framework for cataloguing and weighing a number of complex, interrelated actions. In its initial deployments, the Work Plan elicited detailed and thoughtful responses from evaluated repositories, and led to constructive follow-on planning work, as well as opportunities for further clarifications and guidance. In the larger context of a diverse research ecosystem, the collected Work Plans provided the structural basis to build a broad set of recommendations that could be released as community guidance.

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Author contributions

Nancy J. Hoebelheinrich: conceptualization, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing; Ismael Kherroubi Garcia: writing – original draft, writing – review & editing; Christopher Erdmann: writing – review & editing; Darya Pokutnaya: writing – review & editing; Lisa M. Mayer: writing – review & editing; Julianne Christopher: conceptualization, project administration, writing – review & editing; Christine Kirkpatrick: conceptualization, project administration, writing – review & editing.

Appendix

Appendix I: Pre-Interview Questionnaire: FAIRification and Data Landscape Interview (for Repository Teams and Owners)

Q1 Full name	
Q2 Your project or repository affiliation	
Q3 Your organizational affiliation	
Q4 Your email address	
Q5 Are you a...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. Repository Owner II. *Repository Services & Development team member
<i>N.b.:</i> Questions marked with an asterisk (*) are only to be responded to by repository services & development team members.	
Q6 What is your most common role related to your repository work?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. Repository manager II. Data curator/steward III. Research manager IV. Software Developer V. Web Developer VI. Data wrangler VII. Metadata Specialist VIII. Other (please specify): _____
Q7 Please rate your familiarity with the FAIR Principles for purposes of managing and sharing data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. Familiar and put them into practice II. Familiar but do not currently put them into practice III. Heard of them but not familiar with what they mean IV. Never heard of the FAIR principles
Q8* What percentage of your repository's data has a globally unique and persistent identifier?	
Q9* What is the smallest entity of your repository's data that has a globally unique and persistent identifier?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. Data set/collection II. Data file

	<p>III. Data record</p> <p>IV. Other (please specify):</p> <p>_____</p>
<p>Q10* Please name and describe how each of the identifier types used in your repository's data is created, e.g., IDs for institutions, funding agency, research products, etc.</p>	
<p>Q11 Does your repository use ORCIDs or other digital personal identifiers for researchers?</p>	
<p>Q12* What percentage of your repository's metadata has a globally unique and persistent identifier?</p>	
<p>Q13* What is the smallest entity of your repository's metadata that receives a globally unique and persistent identifier? Please provide an example for each entity, if possible and as applicable.</p>	<p>I. Data set/collection description:</p> <p>_____</p> <p>II. Data file description:</p> <p>_____</p> <p>III. Data record description:</p> <p>_____</p> <p>IV. Other (please specify):</p> <p>_____</p>
<p>Q14 Do your repository's globally unique and persistent identifiers explicitly identify and record versions for data and metadata entities?</p>	<p>I. Yes</p> <p>II. No</p> <p>III. Not sure</p> <p>IV. Other – please specify:</p> <p>_____</p>
<p>Q15* How many metadata fields does your repository require to describe each data entry? (Use your best estimate, or -1 if unknown.)</p>	
<p>Q16* If available, please provide or point to a list of the required metadata fields.</p>	
<p>Q17* How many metadata fields does your repository allow to describe each data entry? (Use your best estimate, or -1 if unknown.)</p>	
<p>Q18* If available please provide or point to a list of the allowed metadata fields.</p>	
<p>Q19 Do you believe the metadata of your repository sufficiently describes the data to meet your end users' discovery needs, i.e.,</p>	<p>I. Yes</p> <p>II. Sometimes;</p> <p>_____</p>

<p>finding and choosing appropriate data for research needs? (If not "Yes," please explain.)</p>	<p>III. No; _____</p>
<p>Q20 Does the metadata describing your repository's data include the identifier of the data being described? (If not "Yes," please explain.)</p>	<p>I. Yes II. Sometimes; _____</p> <p>III. No; _____</p>
<p>Q21 Does your repository track publications that have been produced based on your data or other evidence of data reuse? If Yes, what is the process or method that you use to identify the relevant publications to track or the types of data reuse?</p>	<p>I. Yes; _____</p> <p>II. No III. Don't know</p>
<p>Q22* When using a data set identifier, what standardized retrieval protocol(s) are supported by your repository?</p>	<p>I. None II. Direct download via User Interface (UI) III. Direct download via API command IV. SFTP V. Other (please describe): _____</p> <p>VI. Don't know</p>
<p>Q23* Using a metadata record identifier, what standardized retrieval protocol(s) are supported by your repository?</p>	<p>I. None II. Direct download via UI III. Direct download via API command IV. SFTP V. Other (please describe): _____</p> <p>VI. Don't know</p>
<p>Q24* Have your repository users had any difficulty accessing any data sets? If yes, please provide an explanation for the difficulty, if known.</p>	<p>I. Yes; _____</p> <p>II. No III. Don't know</p>
<p>Q25 If necessary, how do you enforce authentication and authorization in your repository for data download? (Please describe or list any protocols or rules that you use.)</p>	
<p>Q26 Are metadata for your repository's data freely available for download or export? If not, please explain.</p>	<p>I. Yes II. Sometimes</p>

	<p>III. No;</p> <hr/>
<p>Q27 Please describe your response to the following statement: My repository's preservation plan makes an explicit statement and provides assurance that metadata remain available after the corresponding data are removed.</p>	<p>I. Strongly disagree II. Somewhat disagree III. Neither agree nor disagree IV. Somewhat agree V. Strongly agree</p>
<p>Q28* What standard representation format(s) do you support for sharing your data (e.g., CSV, JSON, XML or other)?</p>	<p>I. Comma-separated Values (CSV) II. JSON III. XML IV. Other:</p> <hr/>
<p>Q29* What standard representation format(s) do you support for sharing your metadata (e.g., JSON, YAML, JSON-LD, RDF/XML)?</p>	

Q30* For the following entities (A through F), describe how your repository represents controlled terms. Select all that apply.							
	Free text string (1)	Validated text string (2)	Local code or ID (3)	CURIE (4)	Semantic IRI (5)	Mixed (6)	Other (7)
(A) Data file variable names (e.g., in top row of CSV file) (1)							
(B) Data file values from a short list of options (e.g., checkbox or radio options) (2)							
(C) Data file values from a large managed vocabulary (e.g., diseases, symptoms, or procedures) (3)							
(D) Metadata field or attribute names (e.g., in data element definition) (4)							
(E) Metadata field values from a short list of options (e.g., checkbox or radio options) (5)							
(F) Metadata field values from a large managed vocabulary (e.g., diseases, symptoms, or procedures) (6)							

<p>Q31* Does your repository specify how to reference other relevant data sets or resources in data or metadata? Please describe or point to the policy.</p>	<p>I. Yes; _____</p> <p>II. No</p> <p>III. Not sure</p>
<p>Q32* Does your repository specify a particular set of relations used to describe the related data sets or resources? If Yes, please describe the relations.</p>	<p>I. Yes; _____</p> <p>II. Somewhat</p> <p>III. No</p>
<p>Q33* Does your repository have a list of required and allowed data set topic descriptions that you could provide to us? If yes, please provide or tell us how to acquire it.</p>	<p>I. Yes; _____</p> <p>II. No</p> <p>III. Don't know</p>
<p>Q34 Do you believe the metadata of your repository sufficiently describes the repository's data to meet its end users' re-use needs? (If not "Yes," please explain your answer.)</p>	<p>I. Yes</p> <p>II. Sometimes; _____</p> <p>III. No; _____</p>
<p>Q35 What conditions for access apply to the data and metadata in your repository?</p>	
<p>Q36 Does your repository have a clear and clearly visible data usage license? (Typically, this would mean the license is directly accessible from a link on the front page, it is no longer than a page, and it does not require sophisticated judgments to determine if data can be used.)</p>	<p>I. Yes</p> <p>II. No</p> <p>III. Don't know</p>
<p>Q37 Does your repository have a clear and clearly visible metadata usage license? (Typically, this would mean the license is directly accessible from a link on the front page, it is not longer than a page, and it does not require sophisticated judgments to determine if data can be used.)</p>	<p>I. Yes</p> <p>II. No</p> <p>III. Don't know</p>
<p>Q38 Does your repository support describing where and by what processes the data were created, including processing applied along the way? If so, please describe the support offered by the repository and how the information is made available to users.</p>	<p>I. Yes; _____</p> <p>II. No</p> <p>III. Don't know</p>
<p>Q39 Please list any community standard supported by your repository for describing provenance information.</p>	<p>I. PROV</p> <p>II. CWLProv</p> <p>III. None</p> <p>IV. Don't know</p> <p>V. Other (please explain): _____</p>

<p>Q40 Does your repository's data follow domain-specific (documented) community standards? If so, please list; if not, please describe relevant details.</p>	<p>I. Yes; _____ II. No; _____ III. Not sure</p>
<p>Q41 Does your repository's metadata follow domain-specific (documented) community standards? If so, please list; if not, please describe relevant details.</p>	<p>I. Yes; _____ II. No; _____ III. Not sure</p>
<p>Q42 Are interested in further discussion and collaboration with the project team?</p>	<p>I. Yes II. No III. Maybe</p>
<p>Q43 Please acknowledge that you have completed the survey to the best of your knowledge.</p>	<p>I. Yes II. No</p>

Appendix 2: Generic Work Plan Template

1. Introduction

1.1. Document Status

Document Version: 2.1

Document Status: [Preliminary, Pending Internal Review, Available for External Review, or Ongoing Maintenance]

Last Updated: [YYYY.MM.DD]

1.2. Work Plan Summary

1. **Target Repository:** [Repo Name]
2. **GO FAIR US Coordinator(s):**
3. **Target Repository Program Officer:** [Program officer(s), primary first]
4. **Target Repository Work Plan Representative:** [Program officer or similar with responsibility for directing work tasks]
5. **Project Technical Lead:** [Target Repository or grantee]
6. **Division Name, if applicable:**

The Work Plan tasks outlined in this document are intended for discussion with the repository team. In the discussion process, the repository team will select the most appropriate tasks to undertake at this stage of the project, and the work plan will be updated to reflect the chosen tasks and points of contact for each task. To offer maximum flexibility and a broader general picture, we describe more tasks, in more sections, then will be targeted in the final work plan.

Details about each task, including technical approaches and responsible persons (from the repository and/or from GO FAIR US) will be expanded (in Table 2 and auxiliary documents as needed) during the discussion process. The final Work Plan will include those details.

The Work Plan describes many tasks ambitiously, but less aggressive approaches may be better. We may reference other approaches in the Work Plan Notes, in the Appendix, or during discussions.

1.3. Work Categories

For reference, here we outline the five major categories of work. The Work Plan section details specific tasks.

The major categories of work are:

- **Persistent Identifier (PID) Implementation Strategies**
These strategies focus on having global, persistent, resolvable, and citable identifiers for data and metadata artifacts, and their component entities.
- **Metadata (MD) Improvement Strategies**
These strategies focus on improving descriptions for the data, supporting its discovery, accession, and re-use.
- **Community and Assessment Strategies**
These strategies focus on improving scientific collaboration and sharing within and across domains.
- **Architectural Strategies**
These strategies focus on adopting implementation approaches that make the repositories more broadly and easily interoperable.

- **Additional Specific Strategies**
These strategies focus on repository-specific ways to simplify the implementation of effective and consistent data services.

1.4 Table Key

- **Column Definitions:** The meaning for each column in a specific row is described below.
 - **Item #:** Each category gets its own category number ('1', '2'), while each strategy gets its own sub-number ('1.1', '1.2'). If there are several exclusive strategies to address the same strategic goal, each is appended with a letter ('1.1A', '1.1B').
 - **Priority:** Described tasks (next column) are prioritized as High, Medium, or Low according to their value/dependencies.
 - **FAIRification Task Description:** The strategy name, followed by specific tasks to achieve that strategy (each task is identified with a parenthetical letter ('A')).
 - **Expected Outcome:** The Expected Outcome summarizes the goal of the described work, usually as a functional result.
 - **FAIR Principle:** The FAIR Principle(s) that apply to this strategy. FAIR Principle identifier codes and their descriptions may be viewed in [Appendix A](#).
 - **Metrics:** Proposed metrics for evaluating the usefulness of the strategy. (In some cases metrics may also assess the level of completion of the strategy.)
 - **Resources Required, Dependencies, and Notes:** Additional information about the strategy and corresponding tasks. The Resources Required are summarized as 'Effort'; see Effort and Resource Indicators bullet below for more information.
- **Ordering, priorities, and dependencies**
 - The strategic categories—single-digit sections (1, 2, 3, etc.)—are ordered by notional priority (in part due to dependencies), but community priorities may differ.
 - Within each category, the strategies—numbered items (1.1, 1.2, etc)—are in our suggested priority order, and typically depend on previous strategies.
 - Within each strategy, the tasks—lettered items ((A), (B), etc)—are chronological, and typically depend on previous tasks.
- **Effort and Resource Indicators**
 - Pink text background on the task letters like '(A)' indicates relatively large effort (and associated costs), with lower priority.
 - Effort indicators are conceived as calendar time, yet also roughly correspond to work time. However, the repository goals, architectures, priorities, and chosen approaches may have big impacts on scoping any particular numbered item.
 - = modest effort, 1 week or less for most tasks.
 - = moderate effort, a few weeks to a month for most tasks.
 - = major effort, at least some months will be required overall.
 - = use of highlight color indicates that the highlighted effort is for the highlighted task bullets

2. Work Plan

2.1. Detailed Strategies

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
1	Persistent Identifier (PID) Implementation Strategies					
<p>These strategies focus on identifying the data and metadata artifacts, and their component entities, using identifiers that are globally unique, persistent, resolvable in a browser for humans or computers, and citable in documentation and publications. All of these features increase the value of the underlying data and metadata to the scientific researchers, and to anyone else who wants to discover or work with the resulting resources.</p>						
1.1	<p>High: A, B, C, D</p> <p>Medium: E</p>	<p>PID Strategy: Annotate Data Sets with Appropriate Terms</p> <p>A. Determine appropriate vocabulary(ies) to use</p> <p>B. Apply to existing studies and review with submitters</p> <p>C. Recommend use of the corresponding metadata field and vocabulary to future submitters.</p> <p>D. Display corresponding tags for each dataset, and support in sorting algorithm.</p> <p>E. Implement searching for datasets based on corresponding tags</p>	Dataset search, sort, and/or browse by disease	R1, I2	<p>1. # of time tag is used (e.g., users sort by or search by tag, or click on the tag to learn more)</p> <p>2. % of submissions and datasets identified with one or more of the added tags</p>	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submitter input for existing datasets <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Searching service could be external, in addition to or instead of internal service • GO FAIR US team can help choose appropriate vocabularies; this task would be called out in Final Work Plan

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
1.2	High: A, B, C	<p>PID Strategy: Implement ORCIDs as People Identifiers / RORs as Organization Identifiers</p> <p>A. Use and show ORCIDs of data submitters / RORs of data originators</p> <p>B. Present data-related ORCID / ROR data from ClinicalTrials.gov (if any)</p> <p>C. Recommend use of metadata fields (based on ORCIDs/RORs) to submitters</p>	<p>Establishment of the core practice to simplify later analysis and improve display of metadata (as the common ORCIDs and RORs can be used to connect researchers and organizations across data sets throughout the ecosystem).</p>	R1, R1.2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. # of attributes in system that support ORCIDs/RORs 2. # of unique ORCIDs/RORs referenced in datasets 3) # of submitters defining 'people metadata' with ORCIDs/RORs 	<p>Effort: ⏳ to ⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers must have ORCIDs and be happy to provide them • Maximization of ORCID and ROR adoption and value requires completion of some metadata tasks <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORCIDs effectively 'market' researchers by connecting their diverse products and activities • RORs effectively 'market' organizations by connecting their diverse products and activities • It may be necessary to allow for alternatives or opting out

<p>1.3 A</p>	<p>High: A, B, C, D</p> <p>Medium: E, F</p> <p>Low: G</p>	<p>PID Strategy: Implement Study and Data IDs</p> <p>A. Evaluate cost/benefit of updating any existing study and data identifier schemes to adopt best practices for persistent identifiers (e.g., minimize semantic content, standardize identifier creation, make identifiers resolvable). Agree on final scheme. (existing examples: https://nih.gov/...)</p> <p>B. Allocate unique identifier for each study, associated dataset, and contained data file(s)</p> <p>C. Resolve study, dataset, and data file IDs to views for each entity type</p> <p>D. Make identifiers visible to external systems (Vivli, NDE Discovery Portal, Google Data Search, ...)</p> <p>E. Allow download of entities via API using their identifier.</p> <p>F. Extend to all files within study (track part-of relations)</p> <p>G. Extend to versions of datasets (track relations)</p> <p>H. [Alternate or supplement to E,F,G] Support download of all metadata via JSON-LD or other documented computable format.</p>	<p>Persistent identifiers for content that promote the repository and bring more visitors to it.</p>	<p>F1, F3, A1, R1</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> # of data entity types that have unique identifiers # of visits/resolutions of each identifier type # of external repositories that cite or reference repo's identifier # of citations in papers that use repo's identifiers 	<p>Effort: ⌚⌚⌚</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Must decide if data file identifiers are feasible. <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Task 1.3A targets file-based repositories, 1.3B targets record-based repositories. Choose one or both as appropriate. Datasets are collections of one or more data files; unique IRIs are key for both entity types. Study identifiers may be better as CT.gov or NIH Reporter identifiers, or DOIs referencing those. DOIs are available through doi.datacite.org
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<p>1.3 B</p>	<p>High: A, B, C, D</p> <p>Medium: E, F</p> <p>Low: G</p>	<p>PID Strategy: Implement IDs for Targeted Entity Type(s)</p> <p>A. Identify any existing identifier scheme for the target entity(ies). Evaluate cost/benefit of updating existing identifier schemes to adopt best practices for persistent identifiers (e.g., minimize semantic content, standardize identifier creation, make identifiers resolvable). Agree on final scheme. (existing example if any: ...)</p> <p>B. Allocate unique identifiers for entities of each targeted entity type</p> <p>C. Resolve identifiers to views for each targeted entity type. (Forward any old identifiers to their replacement IRIs.)</p> <p>D. Make identifiers visible to external systems (Vivli, NDE DP, Google Data Search, ...)</p> <p>E. Allow download of targeted entities via API using their identifier</p> <p>F. Extend to all subsidiary targeted entities (track part-of relations)</p> <p>G. Extend to versions of targeted entities (track relations and timestamps)</p> <p>H. [Alternate or supplement to E,F,G] Support download of all metadata via JSON-LD or other documented computable format.</p>	<p>Persistent identifiers for content that promote the repository and bring more visitors to it.</p>	<p>F1, F3, A1, R1</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. # of targeted entity types that have unique identifiers 2. # of visits/resolutions of each identifier by targeted entity type 3. # of external repositories that cite or reference repo's identifiers 4. # of citations in papers that use repo's identifiers 	<p>Effort: ⌚⌚ to ⌚⌚⌚</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to decide which entity types should be targeted • Ability to define an identifier for the targeted entity type in a rigorous, reproducible, intuitive way <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ADVANCED • Entity Types are classes of digital objects that are primary representations in record-based repositories. Detailed documentation regarding Enhanced Interoperability for Entity-Based Repositories will be provided. • Task 1.3A targets file-based repositories, 1.3B targets record-based repositories. Choose one or both as appropriate.
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Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
1.4	<p>High: A, B</p> <p>Medium: C, D, E</p>	<p>PID Strategy: Dataset Citation</p> <p>A. Present to submitters the format and use of citation strings for datasets and data files (using corresponding identifiers) in addition to publications.</p> <p>B. Publish the citation strings on the site for each dataset.</p> <p>C. Identify data sets in the best way possible, and report results to data providers and repo managers</p> <p>D. Add citation information to presented information in the repository.</p> <p>E. Evaluate the prospects of adding dataset identifier/citation fields to ClinicalTrials.gov.</p>	<p>Increased familiarity with, adoption of, and respect for data citations; increased visibility into dataset reuse.</p>	<p>F1, F2, F4</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. # of citations of repo’s citation identifiers 2. # of other references to repo’s dataset citations 3. Altmetrics value for repo’s datasets 	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data citation and identification strategies can work hand-in-hand. • GO FAIR US can suggest best options for citation strings for the repo. • GO FAIR US could offer tracking strategies to detect dataset citations of all of the repo’s datasets. This is a large scope item but would have benefits across many repos.

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
1.5	Medium: A, B	<p>PID Strategy: Auxiliary IDs</p> <p>A. Recommend to submitters the use of shared external identifiers for specifying Projects (tbd), Locations (tbd), and other common identifier types in metadata and data</p> <p>B. Present that information in metadata for the related dataset(s) in user interfaces and via APIs.</p>	<p>Increased access to contextual information about data; increased analytic understanding of the repo's contents; more shared interest in maintaining shared external identifier sources.</p>	F2, F4, R1.2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. # of unique Projects, Locations, and other shared entities represented by repo datasets 2. % of submissions with at least one auxiliary ID (by entity type) 	<p>Effort: ⌚</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need agreement on best Project and Location identifiers to use in across different repositories <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple identifier sources (e.g., Location identifier sources) may be appropriate • Recommend a central tracking system across repositories

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
1.6	<p>High: A</p> <p>Medium: B, C, D</p>	<p>PID Strategy: Provide Shared ID Service</p> <p>A. Identify any collection of identifiers for external resources that is, or could be, used as a shared resource service by other repositories</p> <p>B. Establish that necessary conditions exist for sharing the resource:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. GUPRIs exist and are resolved for each identifier in the collection b. Entity type being shared is well covered c. API mechanism exists to submit, curate, ingest, publish, and search new instances d. Public documentation exists on how to access all services <p>C. Agree with NIH or other funders on policies, practices, and funding arrangements that will be followed to continue supporting the shared resource and assure its persistence.</p> <p>D. Share and announce the service(s)</p>	<p>A single source of truth across multiple organizations and repositories; more complete, reliable, and maintainable source of knowledge; easier adoption of standard identifiers by external parties; allows building of more complex systems by relying on external services.</p>	<p>F2, F4, R1.2</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Metrics of information contained in the service 2. Metrics of requests served by the service. 3. Metrics of organizational adoptions of the service as a primary provider of information. 	<p>Effort: </p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some scale must be achieved before it becomes obvious that the single source of truth is more useful and efficient than multiple sources. • Commitment from senior management to support service in an ongoing way is needed before others will have the confidence to adopt it. <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ADVANCED • Information in the repository must be shared with and open to the relevant community so as to assure transition of information if the system goes down.

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
2		<p>Metadata (MD) Improvement Strategies The metadata strategies improve the descriptions of the data, including their findability, availability and usability. This makes it easier to discover the data, get access to it (if that is appropriate), and re-use it for validation of scientific research or pursuing new scientific discoveries. The strategies also simplify the effort required for scientific communities to work together on shared problems.</p>				

<p>2.1</p>	<p>High: A, B, C, D</p> <p>Medium: E, F</p>	<p>MD Strategy: Standardize Metadata Representation</p> <p>A. Determine metadata schema* for dataset and data file to include at least ClinicalTrials.gov and NDE Data Portal attributes and standardized values, and dataset ID</p> <p>B. Provide effective guidance to data providers on following metadata schema (including controlled vocabularies and other identifiers)</p> <p>C. Complete minimum required metadata for existing projects</p> <p>D. Expose repository’s metadata for machines (download one or all entries by metadata ID using a common API architecture)</p> <p>E. Expose repository’s metadata for people (browse and view by metadata ID)</p> <p>F. Automatically validate metadata and enforce appropriate standards</p>	<p>Each task further prepares the repository for a major upgrade in FAIR capabilities. Completing at least through task (D) enables external repositories and services to offer advanced discovery and re-use of data and metadata, increasing interest and visits.</p>	<p>F2, F4, A2, I1, I2, I3, R1, R1.2</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Datasets <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. # of required attributes supported by all submitted datasets b. # of optional attributes supported (on average) by all submitted datasets 2. Repo APIs <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. # of required attributes supported by repo APIs b. # of optional attributes supported (on average) by repo APIs 3. # of repo-specified metadata attributes (required or optional) that come from, or are mapped to, attributes in community specification 	<p>Effort: ⌚⌚⌚</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ‘minimum required metadata’ attributes should be determined in (A) and described in (B) in order to be filled out in (C). <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • * A metadata schema is a document listing what metadata the repository will support for each entity (e.g., dataset, data file). Metadata schemas should specify ‘required’ and ‘optional’ metadata attributes. • A tool like CEDAR can make the first three tasks relatively simple • A phased approach could adopt basic schema with limited semantics, but with less value • A significantly less desirable alternative to (D) might be to support download of all metadata via JSON-LD or other documented computable format. See Appendix B: Architectural Considerations below for repo-specific observations.
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Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
2.2	<p>High: A, B, C</p> <p>Medium: D, E, F</p>	<p>MD Strategy: Standardize Data Dictionaries</p> <p>A. Adopt a computable Data Dictionary format with semantic capabilities</p> <p>B. Encourage use of new Data Dictionary format (include guidance)</p> <p>C. Expose Data Dictionaries via API</p> <p>D. Provide guidance on selecting vocabularies and terms</p> <p>E. Provide tool for building Data Dictionaries</p> <p>F. Provide evaluation/validation of submitted Data Dictionaries</p>	<p>Uniform machine-parsable data dictionary formats used to describe all data files (provides major discovery and re-use value).</p>	<p>F2, I2, R1, R1.2</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> # and % of submissions with computable semantic Data Dictionaries # and % of submissions with repo-validated Data Dictionaries 	<p>Effort: </p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Needs a Data Dictionary format that is acceptable to most adopters <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A 'computable semantic DD format' exists and can be adopted to desired level of rigor. Each attribute in a Data Dictionary is analogous to a Common Data Element (CDE), which can be shared to build other Data Dictionaries

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
2.3	Medium: A, B, C	<p>MD Strategy: Extend Metadata Representation</p> <p>A. Recommend particular properties when describing contextually related artifacts and encourage adoption of those terms and metadata attributes.</p> <p>B. Recommend particular terms to submitters for describing data provenance, including addressing data integrity concerns.</p> <p>C. Appropriately provide added metadata with corresponding data, including via API</p>	<p>More mature and complete representation of the context of each data set, for better understanding of the data set users.</p>	F2, R1.2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. # of property types used to define contextually related artifacts 2. # of contextually related artifacts referenced (by property type) 	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Previous standardization strategies should be in place. • Tooling to simplify metadata entry is recommended. • Data provenance and data integrity are advanced metadata topics and often depend on specifics of the scientific activity and domain. <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ADVANCED • For (C) See Appendix B: Architectural Considerations below

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
2.4	<p>High: A, B</p> <p>Medium: C</p> <p>Low: D</p>	<p>MD Strategy: Maximize Metadata Adoption</p> <p>A. Offer tooling to fill out metadata</p> <p>B. Provide tracking services that detect the metadata visibility and selection of all repo datasets and report results to data providers and repo managers</p> <p>C. Analyze the degree to which different metadata attributes are provided in submissions, are provided to data analysts by the repo, and contribute to discovery and use of the datasets.</p> <p>D. Extend IDs to versions of metadata</p>	<p>Increased use of tooling that enables more and better metadata to be provided with less effort.</p>	<p>A1, A2, I1, I2, I3, R1</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Percent of metadata completed over time 2. For tooling-assisted metadata, <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Number and % of attributes completed b. Completeness of completed attributes c. Correctness of completed attributes d. Time required to complete metadata 	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking services to detect when repo datasets are selected usually have to be embedded in the repo’s software framework. <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ADVANCED (the tooling and some tracking is straightforward; many metrics are subtle) • Tooling described in (A) exists and can be easily integrated with other systems • Typically versioning is challenging, especially if it isn’t built in from the start

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
2.5	<p>High: A, D</p> <p>Medium: B, C</p> <p>Low: E</p>	<p>MD Strategy: Assess Domain-Centric Strategy</p> <p>A. Using a controlled terminology, characterize domains covered by existing submissions. (Include domains in dataset metadata at convenient time.)</p> <p>B. For each identified domain, determine what specifications (metadata, vocabularies, data formats) exist for that domain. Consider any other target repositories dealing with data in similar domains.</p> <p>C. Hold organization-wide FIPs* workshop to assess domain-specific activities across target repositories.</p> <p>D. Define recommendations to encourage future submitters in those domains to follow domain strategies.</p> <p>E. Recommend path to support adoption of domain guidance for any likely domain.</p>	<p>Identification and adoption of practical domain-specific approaches that each repository can support, and each data contributor can adopt.</p> <p>Knowledge of domain-level adoption of metadata and vocabulary schema and tools across all the participating repositories.</p> <p>Increased community awareness and engagement.</p>	F2, R1.2, R1.3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. # of domains covered by existing submissions 2. # of specifications existing for identified domains 3. # of specifications adopted (as in declared favorable) by this repo for existing domains 4. # of specifications for the relevant domain used by submission (total, and as a % of ideal) 	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement on controlled terminology(ies) to use to characterize domains <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • * A FIP is a FAIR Implementation Profile, which describes some of the implementations a repository has chosen to meet their data and metadata management requirements. A FIPs workshop is an opportunity for repositories to describe, and see others describe, their (potentially shared) implementation choices. • Domain is most often a scientific domain, but can also be oriented to the purpose of the repository (e.g., ‘all data not stored in other repositories’)
3	<p>Community and Assessment Strategies</p> <p>These strategies explicitly address the ability of research communities to work together, to understand and define their own discipline’s needs and any transdisciplinary needs, and to ensure their community’s objectives are well met. When these strategies are implemented, scientific cooperation within specific communities or domains and across domains can be enhanced while making the sharing process more efficient and effective.</p>					

<p>3.1</p>	<p>High: A, B, C</p> <p>Medium: D, E</p>	<p>Assess Strategies for Expanding Domain Researcher Data Sharing and Reuse</p> <p>A. Assess existing Data Sharing and Data Use Agreements to determine whether recommendations can be included that will allow the creation of citations for datasets.</p> <p>B. Solicit feedback from research data submitters or reusers on their experiences with the repository for purposes of assessing and improving submission and download workflows.</p> <p>C. Assess whether there are other places on the repository’s public web pages where examples of recommended formats for citing published outputs from use and reuse of the datasets can be displayed prominently.</p> <p>D. Consider adding information about the repository to repository registries such as fairsharing, SciCrunch, etc. to expand awareness of the repository and its data.</p> <p>E. Assess whether more data usage metrics can be added to the download functions or to associated search methods.</p>	<p>Increased awareness of the repository’s existence, with improvement in both download and upload (sharing) of data sets.</p>	<p>F4, I1</p>	<p>Measure impacts on data usage statistics of expanded sharing of information about the data collections within the repository (e.g., increased number of citations, altmetrics)</p> <p>For a given modification or set of modifications:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. % change in citations 2. % change in altmetrics 3. % change in visits to relevant page type 4. % change in user access requests 	<p>Effort: </p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GO FAIR US staff time <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These strategies more broadly evaluate project-specific opportunities for improving data sharing and re-use, with GO FAIR US team members providing significant analytical support. • Each strategy pursues targeted improvements, at relatively low cost.
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Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
3.2	<p>High: A</p> <p>Medium: B, C, D, E</p>	<p>Develop Key Use Cases</p> <p>A. Identify key interoperability use cases for your repository (things you want to be able to do, or do better).</p> <p>B. If desired, prioritize the use cases to provide input to the Work Plan.</p> <p>C. Assess whether implementing any of the use cases convincingly demonstrates the scientific value of the work (particularly by using quantifiable metrics in a controlled evaluation). If so, define necessary steps to achieve that demonstration.</p> <p>D. Implement necessary steps to achieve demonstration.</p> <p>E. Publish results in appropriate literature.</p>	<p>Improved understanding of repository goals, better Work Plan prioritization, and identification of rigorous criteria to evaluate the value of making your repo more FAIR.</p>	All	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. # of use cases identified, prioritized, and addressed. 2. # of use cases identified as demonstrator use cases. 3. # of evaluated implementations published. 	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GO FAIR US team may help with heavy lifting in steps (C), (D), and (E) • Doing steps (A) and (B) is a valuable contribution to planning and prioritizing of work

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
3.3	<p>High: A, B, C</p> <p>Medium: D</p>	<p>Community Training & Engagement</p> <p>A. Host Metadata for Machine (M4M) workshop* to bring FAIR-motivated participants to greater and shared awareness and interest.</p> <p>B. Embed mini-FIPs workshop** to identify currently adopted domain-specific practices for that community.</p> <p>C. Incorporate training on any of the other in-progress or completed aspects of this Work Plan.</p> <p>D. Support distinct groups in selection and/or creation of initial metadata profiles and needed controlled vocabularies.</p>	<p>Awareness and skills across the repository's user and management communities that increase support for and adoption of FAIR practices.</p>	<p>All, esp. R1.3</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. # of participants completing M4M workshop 2. # of participants completing FIPs or mini-FIPS workshop 3. # of unique participants and participant-hours attending FAIR training activities 4. # of projects receiving consultative support in particular product development (by product type) 5. # of consultation hours provided in particular product development (by product type) 6. # of products generated with consultative support from GO FAIR US 	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each task calls for interest from the targeted participants (both managers and attendees). <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • * An M4M Workshop trains its participants to value, create, and model rich, principled metadata that describes data in their research domains. • ** See Strategy 2.5 for FIPs workshop definitions • Though many hours are expended to host and attend a workshop, the benefit per hour for participants and providers is high. • If participants are skilled software/data experts, shorter but more targeted workshops and training will be optimal.

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
4		<p>Architectural Strategies</p> <p>Architectural strategies concern the actual implementation approaches that are already in place, and that could be adopted by repositories. These are not one-size-fits-all prescriptions, but examples of approaches that could be effective in particular situations. Choosing good architectural approaches for a given repository can make that repository’s data and metadata more easily discovered and used, and those repository products more often cited. Note that Custom observations may be offered in Appendix B: Architectural Considerations.</p>				
4.1 A	Medium: A, B, C	<p>Structure Metadata on Web Pages</p> <p>A. Establish sitemap.xml</p> <p>B. Generate JSON-LD metadata for defined metadata attributes following schema.org specifications</p> <p>C. Publish JSON-LD into script tags in the Study, Dataset, or other entity’s landing page head tags</p>	All defined metadata can be indexed into Google Dataset Search and the NDE Data Portal.	F4, A1, A2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Metadata can be accessed publicly and by Google Dataset Search 2. #/trend of page visits from sources Google Dataset search and plain Google search 	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires ongoing access to web pages for each study, dataset, or entity • Must identify which entity(ies) to provide structured metadata for <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
4.1 B	Medium: A, B, C	<p>Improve Existing Endpoint</p> <p>A. Improve the current (REST, RPC, GraphQL, other) API endpoint to include metadata described in earlier sections</p> <p>B. Make API publicly accessible</p> <p>C. Publicly document the endpoint</p>	Allows metadata and identifier improvements identified in other tasks, and offers flexible public access to metadata.	F4, A1, A2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Queries can be made by anyone (or at least, anyone with an account) 2. # Projects using/analyzing metadata via the API 	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developer with appropriate experience <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing API:

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
4.1C	Low: A, B, C, D	Provide New Metadata API A. Establish sitemap.xml B. Generate JSON-LD metadata for defined metadata attributes following schema.org specifications C. Publish JSON-LD in public endpoint (API) following common web standards (e.g., using HTTPS REST or RPC protocols). D. Publicly document the public endpoint	Provides REST-based querying interface to access system metadata.	F4, A1, A2	1. HTTPS queries can be made by anyone (or anyone with an account, at least) 2. # Projects using/analyzing metadata via HTTPS API	Effort: Dependencies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allowance of the metadata to be publicly accessible. Notes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Priority higher if existing endpoint is non-standard or poorly integrated • Is similar to 4.1, but avoids bespoke patterns • Could be combined with 4.1 • Example REST-based query to get metadata: <a href="https://data.ex.org/metadata/<metadata_ID>">https://data.ex.org/metadata/<metadata_ID>

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
4.2	<p>High: A, B, C</p> <p>Medium: D</p>	<p>Architectural Integration Consult</p> <p>A. Hold a small series of design presentation meetings to understand existing repo system design and goals</p> <p>B. Assess and discuss best approaches to maximize integration with most important external system while minimizing upkeep</p> <p>C. Present and review proposed approach(es) and tradeoffs to enable repository’s choice of implementation</p> <p>D. Implement selected approach</p>	<p>Determines best approach and practices for integrating existing or chosen architecture with external systems like NDE Data Portal</p>	<p>F4, A1, A2</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maintainable interoperable architectural approach(es) defined 2. # external systems supported by design and implementation 	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External systems include Google Data Sets and search, and external community services
5	<p>Additional Specific Strategies</p> <p>A number of other specific strategies can be addressed for certain repositories. The common approaches identified in this section can simplify the implementation of effective data services, and help the repositories in the community provide more consistency to their users.</p>					

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
5.1	<p>High: A, B, C</p> <p>Medium: D</p>	<p>Assess Data Usage License Strategy</p> <p>A. Determine whether an appropriate data license exists to cover the repository’s needs</p> <p>B. If necessary, determine what collection of well-defined data licenses are sufficient to cover (individually) existing data submissions</p> <p>C. Strategize best plan to publish data license for all datasets</p> <p>D. Present appropriate data license in the metadata for each dataset</p>	<p>A defined data license that offers reassurance that the data is available and likely reusable.</p>	R1.1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. % of datasets with data usage license 2. % of datasets with published data usage license 3. % of downloads with data usage license embedded with download 	<p>Effort: ⏳ to ⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A discussion may be necessary about preferred licensing options (n.b., generic government data license) <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An ideal license is generic, but could refer to specific licenses that stand as exceptions • A goal is to maximize sharing, while maintaining flexibility needed by submitters

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
5.2	<p>High: A, B</p> <p>Medium: C</p>	<p>Address Persistence Strategy</p> <p>A. Define repo’s preservation approach (at minimum for metadata)</p> <p>B. Develop and publish Preservation Statement based on the repo’s definition of its preservation approach</p> <p>C. Get overseeing organization’s commitment to Preservation Plan</p>	<p>Publicly vouched metadata preservation strategy that increases user confidence in value of data submission.</p>	A2	<p>1. Data</p> <p>a. Existence of Preservation Statement for data</p> <p>b. Existence of published Preservation Statement for data</p> <p>c. Existence of overseeing organization-endorsed published Preservation Statement for data</p> <p>2. Metadata</p> <p>a. Existence of Preservation Statement for metadata</p> <p>b. Existence of published Preservation Statement for metadata</p> <p>c. Existence of overseeing organization-endorsed published Preservation Statement for metadata</p>	<p>Effort: ⏳⏳</p> <p>Dependencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Program Officers (POs) must be willing to contribute to, publish, and commit to a preservation statement that can capture the repository’s preservation approach • Overseeing organization must be able to provide necessary resources to support the preservation statement. <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core Trust Seal is the high end of preservation statements. • The commitment in (C) is not a requirement for publishing a statement, if the statement is not too ambitious (for example, rehosting metadata in an external repository might not require additional commitments) • Even a minimal statement can be very useful.

Item #	Priority	FAIRification Task Description	Expected Outcome	FAIR Principle	Metrics	Dependencies, resources required, and notes
5.3	Medium: A, B, C	Address AI and LLM Integration A. Define community questions and concerns about intersection of existing data and developments in AI and Large Language Models (LLMs) B. Agree on training, reference, or discussion materials to be presented/hosted by GO FAIR US. C. Present the agreed materials and meetings for the repository to consolidate their knowledge and move forward.	Understanding (and potentially demonstration) of applicability of AI and LLM technologies in data repository	All	1. # of potential applications of AI and LLM to creating and using the repository's resources. 2. Assessed happiness of the participants with the information that was provided.	Effort: ⏳⏳ Dependencies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> GO FAIR US to provide the training and materials. Notes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ADVANCED Curriculum can be standard, or customized to address specific community concerns.

2.2. Task Management Table

This table will be filled out with the selected tasks, their owner and other task management comments.

Item #	Owner	Date of Completion	Notes

Appendix A

The 15 FAIR Principles are first described in the paper The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, and are explained/justified in more detail at the GO FAIR FAIR Principles pages.

F1: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers

F2: Data are described with rich metadata

F3: Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe

F4: (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol

A1.1: The protocol is open, free and universally implementable

A1.2: The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure where necessary

A2: Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available

I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation

I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles

I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

R1.3: (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Appendix B: Architectural Considerations